

Report on Brokerage Activity

D2.5

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the brokerage activities undertaken during the EPOS IP project. It represents the deliverable scheduled at M48 under Task 2.3 “Stakeholder Relations” whose aim has been to promote the EPOS infrastructure among existing scientific users and the wider, evolving, stakeholder community. The D2.5 “Report on Brokerage activity” is directly linked to D2.2 “Report on stakeholders’ engagement” (Task 2.3) officially delivered at M36 (September 2018).

The first version of the D2.5 has been delivered on M24 (September 2017) as internal deliverable and it is currently stored in the EPOS intranet. The M24 version included the list and description of the brokerage activities undertaken during the period M1-M24 and a description of activities planned for the second part of the project.

The present version of D2.5 describes the brokerage activities undertaken during the whole duration of the EPOS IP project.

Introduction

EPOS recognizes the importance of brokerage activities to promote interaction with national research organizations, funding agencies, private sector, society, and other stakeholders inside and outside the EPOS community. The EPOS mission is to enable multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary research for a better understanding of the Earth’s system. Indeed, the range of communities participating in EPOS is a direct measure of its multidisciplinary breath and potential far-reaching impact on the Earth Science community. EPOS will help making a step change in developing new concepts and tools for key answers to scientific and socio-economic questions concerning geo-hazards and geo-resources as well as Earth science applications to the environment and to human welfare.

To reach this goal EPOS has to communicate with very diverse audiences including not only solid Earth scientists but scientists belonging to disciplines outside the solid Earth domain as well as government representatives, the private sector and, critically, society. The main objective of the brokerage activities EPOS has undertaken during the project has been to meet and interact with these different stakeholders belonging to heterogeneous communities that speaks different, specific, technical and scientific languages in order to engage them.

Successful engagement will enable maximum exploitation of EPOS in terms of both a large volume of used services and a large number of users. Reaching out to potential new communities and supporting them to become active users and/or providers of EPOS is also essential to engage them. Engagement requires dissemination, communication, involvement, active participation and direct contributions to the EPOS enterprise. Communities to be engaged are influenced by and will influence EPOS by directly contributing to the activities. In other words, they have a double pro-active role in characterizing the EPOS communication strategies and consequently the highest priority.

The Report on Brokerage Activity (D2.5) aims to list and describe the brokerage activities undertaken during the whole duration of the EPOS IP project, from October 1, 2015 to September 30, 2019 (M1-48).

Description of the Brokerage Activities

A summary of the brokerage activities undertaken during the EPOS IP project (10/2015 – 09/2019) is provided per the period M1-M24 and M25-M48 in tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1. List of Brokerage activities performed in the period M1-M24.

Title	Date	Place	Type of audience	Attendants	Beneficiary WP *
Scientific drilling – ICDP data integration	11-12 /11/ 2015	Potsdam (Germany)	SC; HE&R	10	19.UU WP15
EGU 2016	17-22 /04/ 2016	Vienna (Austria)	SC; PM; PS	13,650	1.INGV WP2
2 nd TEP event	10 /05/ 2016	Prague (Czech Republic)	PS	30	24.CNR WP12
European OBS and MSP workshop (ORFEUS Annual meeting)	27-28 /10/ 2016	Dubrovnik (Croatia)	SC; HE&R	74	4.ETHZ WP8
IS-EPOS Platform Training and Brokerage event	21 /11/ 2016	Katowice (Poland)	PS; HE&R; GP	37	10.IGF PAS WP14
DIAS Industry Information Day	20 /12/ 2016	Frascati (Italy)	PS	100	24.CNR WP12
EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop	19-20 /01/ 2017	Bergen (Norway)	SC; HE&R	45	5.UiB WP6
EGU 2017	23-28 /04/ 2017	Vienna (Austria)	SC; PM; PS	14,496	1.INGV WP2
9 th Meeting Group of Senior Officials on Global RI	15-16 /05/ 2017	Naples (Italy)	PM; SC; HE&R	30	1.INGV WP2
2 nd Nordic EPOS meeting	14-16 06 / 2017	Helsinki (Finland)	SC; HE&R	50	21.UH WP4
Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) workshop	5-7 09 / 2017	Lenzburg (Switzerland)	SC; HE&R	130	4.ETHZ WP8
ORFEUS Workshop	25-27 /10/ 2017	Lisbon (Portugal)	SC; HE&R	120	4.ETHZ WP8
EPOS-Norway SESF Workshop	1-3 /11/ 2017	Bergen (Norway)	SC; HE&R	25	5.UiB WP6
European OBS workshop	6-7 /11/ 2017	Paris (France)	SC; HE&R	25	4.ETHZ WP8
Technical Workshop on InternetMacroseismology	14-15 /11/ 2017	Ljubljana (Slovenia)	SC	41	22.EMSC WP8
AGU Fall Meeting	11-15 /12/ 2017	New Orleans, Louisiana (USA)	SC; PM; PS	24,000	1.INGV WP2

Legend for Type of audience: Scientific Community (SC); Higher Education and Research (HE & R); Policy Makers (PM); Private Sector (PS); General Public (GP).

* Event organized or participated by EPOS IP Beneficiary in the framework of a specific work package

Table 2. List of Brokerage activities performed in the period M25-M48.

Title	Date	Place	Type of audience	Attendants	Beneficiary WP *
EGU	8-13 /04/ 2018	Vienna (Austria)	SC; PM; PS	15,075	1.INGV WP2
EPOS INFO-DAY	29-30 /05/ 2018	Ljubljana (Slovenia)	SC	50	1.INGV WP2
36 th ESC General Assembly	2-7 /0 / 2018	Valletta (Malta)	SC; HE&R	300	1.INGV WP2
Arctic Geoinves workshop	29 /10/ 2018	Kemi, Finland	Other	20	26.UOULU WP14
ORFEUS Annual Meeting	12-14 /11/ 2018	Athens (Greece)	SC; HE&R	80	4.ETHZ WP8
Research Infrastructure Fair	19-21 /11/ 2018	Jachranka (Poland)	SC; HE&R; PS	90	10.IGF PAS WP14
EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop	23-24 /01/ 2019	Bergen (Norway)	SC; HE&R;	50	5.UiB WP6
EPOS User Feedback Group	6-7 / 03 / 2019	teleconference	SC	40	5.UiB WP6
EGU	7-12 /04/ 2019	Vienna (Austria)	SC; PM; PS	16,250	1.INGV WP2
EPOS User Feedback Group	3-5 /06 / 2019	Prague, Czech Republic	SC	40	5.UiB WP6
TCS Geomagnetic Observations meeting with Users and Providers	18-19 /06/ 2019	Prague (Czech Republic)	SC	40	14. IG ASCR WP13
The EPOS platform and innovation potential	26 /09/ 2019	Madrid (Spain)	SC; PM	50	1.INGV WP2
EPOS practical solutions to Data Interoperability & FAIRness	27 /09/ 2019	Madrid (Spain)	SC	50	1.INGV WP2

Legend for Type of audience: Scientific Community (SC); Higher Education and Research (HE & R); Policy Makers (PM); Private Sector (PS); General Public (GP).

* Event organized or participated by EPOS IP Beneficiary in the framework of a specific work package

Brokerage activities undertaken in 2015-2016

Scientific Drilling - ICDP Data Integration Event, Potsdam (Germany), 11 and 12 November 2015.

The “Scientific drilling – ICDP data integration” brokerage event was organised by the University of Uppsala. The meeting was attended by members of the Operational Support Group of the International Continental Scientific Drilling Program (ICDP, located at GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences), GFZ data expert and members of EPOS TCS Geological Information and Modeling in charge (WP15) of tasks 15.6 “Scientific drilling data” (UU) and 15.7 “3D models” (GFZ). The aim was to present the WP tasks and discuss how to access and integrate ICDP data in EPOS. The main impact of the event has been the consolidation of the awareness about EPOS in ICDP and the foundation of a good collaboration with data provider.

European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria, 17- 22 April 2016

The EGU General Assembly, with hundreds of scientific sessions and side events is always participated by thousands of scientists (most of them being students) and exhibitors from the private sector from all around the world was a great visibility opportunity for EPOS. In particular, during the 2016 EGU General Assembly organised 619 scientific sessions and 321 side events and brought together 13,650 scientists and 80 exhibitors from 109 countries. EPOS visibility during the Assembly has been ensured by a dedicated exhibit booth where the EGU participants have been invited to know more about EPOS initiatives, goals and activities, receiving complete information and gadgets. EPOS also lead a session on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services in Geosciences and a Splinter Meeting. The goal of the EPOS session was to discuss the integration of existing data and services and to share strategies and visions to tackle technological challenges and scientific missions with stakeholders coming from scientific fields complementary to solid Earth science, such as marine and space sciences, ICT, HPC and e-science. Particular attention has been devoted to the efforts needed to provide access to stakeholders not belonging to the scientific community, as well as to disseminate data products of relevance for tackling societal challenges like geo-hazards and geo-resources.

2nd Thematic Exploitation Platform (TEP) event (ESA), Prague (Czech Republic), 10 May 2016

The 2nd TEP co-location event organized by ESA in Prague (30 participants), allowed the TCS Satellite Data partners to meet the industry working in the field of e-infrastructures and satellite data exploitation. This event also allowed the TCS Satellite Data to discuss with some private sector actors around the EPOS infrastructure and its main objectives, by mainly focusing on the needs of Satellite Data community and the challenges that the TCS Satellite Data is going to face in the next years.

European Mobile Seismic Pools (MSP) and Ocean Bottom Seismometers parks (OBS) coordination workshop in the framework of the ORFEUS Annual Meeting, Dubrovnik, Croatia, 27-29 October 2016

The goal of ORFEUS Annual Observatory Coordination meeting was to provide to network and station operators an opportunity to meet, exchange and discuss experiences and knowledge on recent and current developments in seismic network operations, data management and exchange and community tools, with a particular focus on the Balkans. In the framework of the Annual Meeting, the TCS Seismology (WP8) and ORFEUS European Research Initiatives sponsored the European Mobile Seismic Pools (MSP) and Ocean Bottom Seismometers parks (OBS) coordination workshop (27-28 October). The aim of the event was to efficiently integrate data from these communities within the European Integrated Data Archive

(EIDA: www.orfeus-eu.org/eida), a key infrastructure of ORFEUS and EPOS architectures. 74 people from 26 countries participated to the meeting.

IS-EPOS Platform Brokerage event, Katowice, Poland, 21 November 2016

This event, organised by the TCS Anthropogenic Hazards (WP14), has been addressed to the scientific community, students at any level and representatives from industry. The main purpose of the event was to inform about anthropogenic seismicity and the state-of-the-art knowledge, tools and data. The workshops also provided user's feedback and fostered the development of new ideas regarding the use of integrated research infrastructure, leading to new insights regarding user requirements.

Copernicus Data and Information Access Service (DIAS) Industry Information Day, Frascati, Italy, 20 December 2016.

The TCS Satellite Data (WP12) members attended this brokerage event focused on the interactions between private sector and European institutions. In this framework, an important initiative, carried on by ESA and EC DG-Growth, aimed at creating and enabling a European EO Data ecosystem for research and business, was represented. The establishment of DIAS is of high relevance for the TCS Satellite because DIAS could be the natural infrastructure for a large number of EO services, significantly enhancing the quality and the quantity of DDSS provided by the TCS Satellite Data.

Brokerage activities undertaken in 2017

EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop, Bergen, Norway, 19-20 January 2017

EPOS-Norway organised the EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop both for the EPOS-Norway project partners and for external parties. The overall purpose of the workshop was to meet and discuss the project, and for external participants to learn more about EPOS. During the first day session there have been contributions from all the work packages and partners. On the second day, different interest groups met separately to discuss central issues and prepare for upcoming tasks.

European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria, 23- 28 April 2017

The EGU General Assembly, with hundreds of scientific sessions and side events is always participated by thousands of scientists (most of them being students) and exhibitors from the private sector from all around the world was a great visibility opportunity for EPOS. In particular, during the 2017 EGU General Assembly organised 649 scientific sessions, 88 short courses and 322 side events and brought together 14,496 scientists and 80 exhibitors from 107 countries. EPOS visibility during the Assembly has been ensured, like the previous year, by a dedicated exhibit booth where participants could receive information about the Research Infrastructure, and the EPOS IP project, being informed about the EPOS achievements. In the booth, the EPOS community had organized "demonstrator sessions" presenting the Research Infrastructure, services and other specific topic. Moreover, at the stand the EPOS brochure and the 10 EPOS TCS Flyers have been distributed to inform about the EPOS services and their implementation. EPOS lead a co-organized session on Integrated Research Infrastructures and Services. EPOS has been also presented at the ENVRIplus booth Stand.

9th Meeting of the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures (GRI), Naples, Italy 15-16 May 2017

The Meeting has been co-organised by EPOS and by EMBRC and jointly hosted by the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV) and the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN) on behalf of the Italian government, “Ministero dell’Istruzione, dell’Università e della Ricerca” (MIUR). The Group of Senior Officials (GSO) has been set up in 2008 by the G8+5 to establish a non-binding and open forum for policy exchanges on global research infrastructures and since then it has developed a collaboration framework including a definition of GRIs. The GSO proactively works to identify opportunities for international collaboration among Research Infrastructures proposed by its members. During the meeting in Naples, the GSO had the opportunity of better understanding the peculiarities and goals of EPOS and EMBRC before analysing five Case Studies of initiatives for the development of large research infrastructures based on international cooperation principles and discussed policy issues concerning sharing and management of data and services, open innovation and global excellent-driven access of GRIs.

2nd Nordic EPOS meeting in Helsinki, Finland, 14 - 16 June 2017

The 2nd regional Nordic EPOS meeting has been organised by the Institute of Seismology, University of Helsinki, Finland. The goal of the Nordic EPOS meeting was to develop the Nordic EPOS dimension by finding Nordic collaboration forms in EPOS TCS and governance work and to discuss the practicalities, advances and the work done within the EPOS framework. Nordic EPOS meeting was open to participants from all the fields represented in EPOS. To further promote the aspect of Nordic co-operation and collaboration, the meeting has been arranged back-to-back with the 48th Nordic Seismology Seminar.

Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) workshop, Lenzburg (Switzerland), 5-7 September 2017

The Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Assessment (PSHA) workshop has been by ETH Zurich. The workshop brought together around 130 leading experts on PSHA from around the globe to discuss the state-of-the-art of the practice as well as well as future directions for probabilistic seismic hazard assessment at a local, national, and transnational scale. The workshop adopted a holistic point of view (i.e. interdisciplinary, multiple spatial- and temporal scales), critically reflecting all elements of modern PSHA. Distinguished keynote speakers introduced a range of topics, and participants presented oral and poster contributions. Time for discussions and networking was properly allocated. During the event participants reflected on emerging challenges, such as time-dependence, earthquake interactions, anthropogenic seismicity, model validation, simulation based PSHA, communication of hazard results and procedural requirements for ensuring robustness, especially in the context of PSHA for critical facilities. On day three, the workshop focused specifically on the needs of community and harmonization projects, such as the next-generation European PSHA and on hazard and risk services in Europe as part of EPOS.

ORFEUS and EPOS Seismology Workshop, Lisbon, Portugal, 25-27 October 2017

The EPOS Seismology Workshop was part of the 2017 ORFEUS Annual workshop with a focus on Seismology on the Iberian Peninsula and in Northern Africa and the EMSC General Assembly. The main goals of the EPOS seismology workshop were to engage the European seismological community not directly involved in the EPOS-IP project, focusing on demonstration, discussion, and hands-on experience of EPOS Seismology data and products services. The workshop scientifically focused on a) hands-on experience of EPOS-Seismology services with a special focus on EPOS GNSS services and their interconnection with seismology, and b) on

Seismology on the Iberian Peninsula and in Northern Africa. During this workshop, on the evening of October 26, the annual EMSC General Assembly also took place.

EPOS-Norway SESF Workshop, Bergen, Norway, 1-3 November 2017

On 1-3 November 2017, EPOS-Norway project organised a workshop in Bergen where 25 students and scientists attended. The workshop was the first of the planned activities of the SESF (Solid Earth Science Forum), organized for the purpose of creating a constant feedback mechanism for the developments of the EPOS-Norway web-portal. The goal of the workshop was to test the newest version of a software developed by CMR (Christian Michelsen Research), through dedicated exercises designed for solving relevant scientific questions. The Enlighten web-tool makes it possible to combine large data sets from different disciplines within Solid Earth Science, giving the users more freedom and new possibilities working with their research. The workshop was organised by the EPOS partner UiB. The first day of the workshop was optional, and dedicated to introducing Scientific Python. The second day, the participants applied Enlighten-web for solving scientific questions based on data from the Norland area.

European OBS technical workshop, Paris, France, 6-7 November 2017

The 2017 European OBS technical workshop has been held at the *Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (IPGP)* and included a visit tour of INSU-IPFP OBS. The goal of the workshop was to improve the number, quality and compatibility of European OBSs by finding or creating common projects and better ways to communicate. Technicians and engineers from all European OBS facilities have been invited to participate. The workshop has been sponsored by the EPOS that supports OBS parks to put their waveform data onto FDSN-compatible data centers through EIDA nodes within ORFEUS.

Technical Workshop on Internet Macroseismology, Ljubljana, Slovenia, 14-15 November 2017

The Technical Workshop on Internet Macroseismology has been co-organized by the Slovenian Environment Agency (ARSO) and the, European Mediterranean Seismological Centre (EMSC) with the support EPOS. During the workshop, European seismologists from 19 organisations discussed on how macroseismic data, i.e. earthquake intensity data derived from felt earthquake reports, could be better collected and exchanged between seismological institutes in the future. The European and Mediterranean situation is quite complex as at least 36 seismological institutes in 24 countries all collect felt reports using their own or a standardised online questionnaire or using a smartphone app. When an earthquake is only felt within the border of one country, likely only one responsible national institute (except in Germany or Spain) will have all the data and can properly map the earthquake impact. However, in case of cross-border felt earthquakes, the gathering of macroseismic data is fragmented between different institutes who are all responsible for the macroseismic information in their country. Hence, sharing intensity values derived from online questionnaires is essential and would strongly facilitate mapping the impact of trans-frontier-felt earthquakes in the future. During the workshop 17 studies on national and international methodologies, objectives, collecting systems and case studies were presented. Presently, apart from rapid information about the felt area from EMSC and a few cross-border initiatives, there is no coordinated and comprehensive system to collect, interpret and present macroseismic data on a European level. During the discussion numerous ideas were exchanged how to harmonise the data to facilitate the exchange. It was decided to develop a new proposal for an ESC (European Seismological Commission) working group that can concentrate on these challenges in macroseismic data

exchange in Europe, and to propose a special session dedicated to Internet Macroseismology at the forthcoming ESC General Assembly in Malta (2-7 Sep 2018).

American Geophysical Union (AGU) Fall Meeting, New Orleans, Louisiana (USA), 11-15 December 2017

The AGU Fall Meeting is the premier Earth and Space science meeting in the world; it is organised on an annual basis. The meeting brings together leaders from academia, government, and the private sector, and it is the ideal platform to present research, hear about the latest discoveries, scientific developments in earth and space science, trends, and challenges. In particular, the 2017 Fall Meeting has been attended by more than 24,000 participants from 113 countries. The EPOS community attended the event by giving talks and presenting posters in many different sessions (e.g. during the Session “International Collaboration on Environmental Data and Service Infrastructures”, EPOS presented “EPOS Thematic and Integrated services for European Solid Earth Sciences: the EPOS Integrated Approach.”; during the Session “International Collaboration on Environmental Data and Service Infrastructures, Practices, Access, and Technologies”, EPOS presented “The Contribution for Improving GNSS Data and Derived Products for Solid Earth Sciences Promoted by EPOS-IP”, “Contributions of the German Research Center for Geosciences (GFZ) to the EPOS Implementation Phase).

Brokerage activities undertaken in 2018

European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria, 08- 13 April 2018

The EGU General Assembly, with hundreds of scientific sessions and side events is always participated by thousands of scientists (most of them being students) and exhibitors from the private sector from all around the world, is a great visibility opportunity for EPOS. In particular, in 2018, EGU General Assembly organised 666 scientific sessions, 68 short courses and 294 side events and brought together 15,075 scientists and 80 exhibitors from 106 countries. EPOS, as usual, participated with a booth that served as a meeting point for the community: a place where scientists have the chance to learn more about the EPOS RI and its Thematic Core Services. Flyers, Brochures and gadgets has been also distributed. During the whole week, the EPOS Community members organized “demonstrator sessions”, and gave presentation talks about the Research Infrastructure, the TCS services and related topics. Furthermore, EPOS organised the session called “*Integrating data and services in solid Earth sciences*”. The goal of this session was to discuss the integration of existing community-specific data infrastructures and data services into a multidisciplinary platform in the domain of solid Earth sciences to be accessible to a wide range of users and stakeholders. The session received contributions from scientists, research infrastructures, e-Infrastructure providers, ICT experts, managers, and communicators involved in activities for implementing data and service provision of relevance for solid Earth science. The main objective was to share strategies and visions to tackle technological and scientific challenges. The session also aimed at emphasizing the importance of global data infrastructures in solid Earth sciences, welcoming contributions from key international initiatives. Particular attention has been given to the efforts needed to provide access for stakeholders not belonging to the scientific community as well as to disseminating data products of relevance for the societal challenges like geo-hazards and geo-resources. EPOS Session promoted a stimulating discussion and a debate on the challenge of creating federated data services within and across the communities belonging to solid Earth sciences.

EPOS Info-Day Ljubljana, Slovenia, 29 - 30 May 2018

The EPOS Info Day has been organized in the framework of the Communication and Dissemination activities of WP2 by INGV in collaboration with ZRC SAZU, Slovenia, the local co-organizer and IGF PAS, Poland. This initiative, scheduled in the EPOS Communication Plan, was dedicated to disseminate, inform, engage and involve potential users and stakeholders of the EPOS infrastructure and its integration plan. The EPOS Info-Day was an opportunity to present the global perspectives of the EPOS pan-European infrastructure and to highlight its impact for solid-Earth science. The event was targeted to potential users and stakeholders from the Eastern Adriatic area: scientists from research organizations and universities, policy-makers, and other people interested in learning about EPOS, its provision in terms of scientific data, products and services as well as to foster interregional and international cooperation in an enlarged Europe, across its borders. On the 29th afternoon, the Info-Day focused on the strategic implications of participating in the EPOS integration plan and to the construction of the new EPOS research infrastructure. On the 30th morning, the scientific and technological impact was discussed, with a particular focus on scientific data and service provision. Contributions from several Thematic Core Services (Seismology, GNSS Data & Products, Geomagnetic Observations, and Geological Information and Modelling) were scheduled in the agenda, together with open discussions to foster effective and open exchanges of ideas. The event welcomed 52 participants from 14 countries, 5 of them (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Kosovo, Rep. of Macedonia, Montenegro), currently not part of EPOS. In the evening of 29th May 2018, a visit in Ljubljana downtown related to signs of 1895 earthquake was led by the mag. Ina Cević (President of European Seismological Commission, Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, Seismology office).

36th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Valletta, Malta, 2-7 September 2018

EPOS participated in the 36th General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission (ESC) with a booth set up as a meeting and information point for all conference participants who wanted to know more about EPOS. Following the successful “EGU model”, a number of presentations have been scheduled at the booth about EPOS, EPOS services and activities. The EPOS community member, participating to the event organised at the booth a series of “hands-on” sessions providing a live experience on how to use the already operational EPOS Seismology services. These sessions lasted one hour each and hosted 20 participants at a time. A detailed schedule of times and topics has been made available on the EPOS website before the meeting, and at the EPOS booth during the conference. EPOS, and in particular EPOS Seismology, organised the session “Seismological e-infrastructures and their data and products services” hold on Monday 3 September. Also, after the poster session, EPOS Seismology hosted an “information meeting” open to all conference participants, followed by an EFEHR coordination meeting targeted towards the further development of the EFEHR consortium. EFEHR is a non-profit network of organisations and community resources aimed at advancing earthquake hazard and risk assessment in the European-Mediterranean area. EFEHR is not replacing national or local efforts, it is supporting and enriching them. EFEHR constitutes one of the three service domains in the Thematic Core Service (TCS) Seismology within the European Plate Observatory System (EPOS). The two others are ORFEUS (waveform services) and CSEM-EMSC (seismological products services).

Arctic Geoinvest meeting & workshop, Kemi, Finland, 29 October 2018

The Arctic Geoinvest meeting & workshop took place at the University of Applied Sciences in Kemi, Finland. Arctic Geoinvest is an Innovation management with multidisciplinary organizations mainly from Northern Finland. Participated to the event scientific Institutions, industrial and municipal representatives. Arctic Geoinvest draws on a versatile and strong collaboration network to promote the usage and deployment of Arctic geoinnovations and related technical applications in companies in the field.

Speakers belonging to different projects have been invited. EPOS IP contributed with the oral presentation: "EPOS AH as a tool in mining industry education and research". Networking was the main aim of the event with the objective to advance the development of Arctic area of Finland.

ORFEUS Annual Meeting, Athens, Greece, 12-14 November 2018

The 2018 ORFEUS Annual Observatory Meeting and Workshop, co-sponsored by EPOS Seismology, was hosted by the National Observatory of Athens. The workshop was supported by the Hellenic Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO, the UNESCO Chair on Natural Hazards in the Geosphere, the Hydrosphere and the Atmosphere, established at NOA in 2006. The workshop focused on Strong-Motion Seismology and Engineering Seismology. Core thematic areas were: T1 - Coordination and knowledge transfer among Euro-Mediterranean networks and observatories; T2 - ORFEUS / EPOS strong-motion services and products; T3 - Challenges in Strong-Motion and Engineering Seismology and the role of ORFEUS in serving the community to face them; T4 - Best practices in site characterisation; T5 - EPOS NFOs data integration. A rich discussion took place during the workshop that brought together experiences and ideas from the operational and research communities.

1st Scientific and Technical Conference of the EPOS-PL project, Jachranka, Poland, 19-21 November 2018

The 1st Scientific and Technical Conference dedicated to the EPOS-PL project was organised by the Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences (IG PAS), EPOS IP partner. Representatives of entrepreneurs and scientific institutions interested in the Research Infrastructure EPOS-PL were invited to the discussion. The first day of the conference was dedicated to the main pillars the EPOS. The goals and achievements, as well as the principles of integration of individual Thematic Core Services included in the European EPOS programme were presented. The second day of the conference was dominated by the Research Infrastructure Fair. The achievements of individual Research Infrastructure Centers of the EOPS-PL project were presented. Research and analyses carried out with the use of the Research Infrastructure EPOS-PL were the main topics of the afternoon session of the second day of the conference. The last day of the conference was characterised by meetings in individual thematic tasks.

Brokerage activities undertaken in 2019**EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop 2019, Bergen, Norway, 23-24 January 2019**

The EPOS-Norway Annual Workshop brought together more than fifty participants: partners and external parties related to EPOS, as well as anyone interested in learning more about EPOS-Norway, the Norwegian node of the European Plate Observing System. The first day (23 January) was dedicated to presentations from partners and collaborators of EPOS-N, and was open for all interested parties. The second day involved more technical discussions and various internal meetings. The project's External Advisory Board (EAB) had their

third annual meeting to evaluate the progress of the EPOS-N project, and the Solid Earth Science Committee (SESC) and Project Management Board (PMB) also had their first meetings of the year.

EPOS User Feedback Group (UFG) webinar and videoconference, 6-7 March 2019

The EPOS Service Coordination Board (SCB) agreed to set up a coordinating group between Thematic Core Services (TCS), and Integrated Core Service (ICS) people to ensure common understanding on the IT requirements, expectations and offerings, and the ICS development plan. The first event took place remotely between 6-7 March 2019 with 2h webinar in one day and 1-2h video teleconference the second day. During this meeting, the aims and structure of EPOS was explained to UFG members, as well as the whole procedure of collection of feedback. Feedback from the UFG workshop raised a new list of requirements which were further taken into account into development of the ICS system and preparation for the operational phase.

European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly, Vienna, Austria, 07-12 April 2019

The EGU General Assembly, with hundreds of scientific sessions and side events is always participated by thousands of scientists (most of them being students) and exhibitors from the private sector from all around the world was a great visibility opportunity for EPOS. In particular, during the 2017 EGU General Assembly organised 683 scientific sessions, 87 short courses and 338 side events and brought together 16,273 scientists and 80 exhibitors from 113 countries. EPOS visibility throughout the event has been ensured through the dedicated exhibit booth, in which EPOS disseminated updated information about the service implementation and data provision, as well distributed booklets, flyers and gadgets to the visitors. Inside the booth, the EPOS community provided demo presentations in the booth concerning the Integrated and Thematic Core Services. EPOS invited scientists, research infrastructures, e-Infrastructure providers, ICT experts, managers, and communicators involved in activities for implementing data and service provision of relevance for solid Earth science to submit contributions. Also, EPOS collaborated to the organisation of the activity undertaken in the European Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community booth located.

EPOS User Feedback Group (UFG) testing workshop, Prague, Czech Republic, 3-5 June 2019

The second EPOS User Feedback Group Workshop invited users to test interoperability and access to data and services provided by TCS and ICS. The aims of the workshop were 1) to test the available functionality of the EPOS website interface (ICS GUI) within predefined tasks by domain experts, 2) to monitor the interaction of the experts with the system, and collect feedback on the usability of the system (appearance, functionality, performance, bugs, etc.) by filling in an evaluation form, and 3) to collect a list of deliverables for improving the system and to prioritize these toward the September milestone.

TCS Geomagnetic Observations meeting with Users and Providers, Prague, Czech Republic, 18-19 June 2019

The TCS Geomagnetic Observations (WP13) team invited users and providers of geomagnetic and magnetotelluric data to the EPOS TCS Geomagnetic Observations meeting with Users and Providers organised at the Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, in Prague on 18 and 19 June 2019. The recent state of integration of geomagnetic and magnetotelluric data and services has been discussed and future development outlined. Participants contributed on data collection and usage. The meeting has been held on the occasion of the 180th anniversary of the regular magnetic observations at Prague Observatory.

The EPOS platform and innovation potential, Madrid, Spain, 26 September 2019

This event has been organised in the framework of the EPOS IP final meeting. It has been a great opportunity for the EPOS external participants to gain an insight of the community building and the data and service provision established by the EPOS IP Thematic Core Services (TCS). Also, the implemented Integrated Core Services and the status of the EPOS Delivery Framework have been presented. The event has been enriched by live demonstrations of the ICS-C prototype and TCS Services.

EPOS practical solutions to Data Interoperability & FAIRness, Madrid, Spain, 27 September 2019

Experts, scientists, representatives of international initiatives and Research Infrastructure participated to share experiences and practices on data interoperability and FAIRNESS, to discuss practices and existing gaps between principles and practices, and to discuss services implemented and operated by Research Infrastructures in order to better understand how to federate them in broader pan-European frameworks.

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Conclusions

EPOS IP project beneficiaries and TCS communities' members participated to twenty-seven (27) brokerage events since the beginning of the project until its end.

The objectives of the organisation and participation to the brokerage events was to present EPOS, its data and service provision, the TCSs Communities and to prepare the floor for co-operations between participants, paving the way for future co-operations.

In particular, these brokerage events offered the opportunity to:

- raise the awareness of EPOS among the different stakeholder's categories,
- share strategies and visions to tackle the technological challenges and the scientific missions, emphasizing the importance of global data infrastructures,
- exchange and discuss experiences to foster the development of new ideas regarding the use of integrated research infrastructure leading to new insights regarding user requirements,
- engage the different stakeholders in the EPOS Delivery Framework enlarging its pan-European dimension.